

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Democratic Health Questionnaire (DHQ): Version for Institutions providing Non-formal Educational Programmes

Variable report & codebook related to the international
dataset [10.5281/zenodo.15349145](https://zenodo.org/record/15349145)

Project Title	Democracy meets arts: critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
Grant Agreement No.	101094217
Project Acronym	Critical ChangeLab
EC Call	HORIZON-CL2-2022-DEMOCRACY-01-04
Partner responsible for creation	Institute for Social Research in Zagreb – ISRZ
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Creation date	7.3.2025.
Place of publication	Zagreb, Croatia
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15349337
DOI of associated dataset	10.5281/zenodo.15349145
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Critical ChangeLab is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101094217. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

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Glossary

AE	Ars Electronica
ALTEREURO	European Alternatives
Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
DHQ	Democracy Health Questionnaire
ISRZ	Institute for Social Research in Zagreb
KERSNIKOVA	Kersnikova Institute
LATRA	LATRA
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
UB	University of Barcelona
UOULU	University of Oulu
WAAG	Waag Futurelab

1 Short description of Democratic Health Questionnaire (DHQ)

The Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ) was developed as part of the Horizon Europe Critical ChangeLab project to assess the democratic health of schools and institutions offering non-formal educational programs across ten partner countries.

Designed as a self-assessment tool, the DHQ enables schools and educational institutions to evaluate their current state of democratic health and plan future initiatives to enhance this vital aspect of their organization.

Two versions of the DHQ have been created: one for schools and another for institutions providing non-formal educational programmes. The questionnaire examines the democratic health of educational institutions by assessing the importance, current status, and five-year expectation regarding 26 democratic practices and four democratic values. Ten language versions of questionnaire for institutions providing non-formal educational programmes are available at:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13767190>

2 Implementation of the Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ)

The DHQ was administered centrally using Alchemer, an online survey platform. As the task leader, ISRZ was responsible for setting up different versions of the DHQ, with each partner translating master version (English) into their national language.

All partners were responsible for distributing the questionnaire link to educational institutions providing non-formal educational programmes.

The following criteria guided the selection of educational institutions for participation:

- Institutions providing educational services to learners aged 11 to 18
- Exclusion of informal groups from participation
- Offering educational programmes which have significant length, as well as the stability in providing educational programmes
- Serving groups of learners, rather than individuals
- Inclusion of institutions offering both free and paid educational activities
- Ensuring geographic diversity in institution locations
- Providing education both in person and online

- Covering a wide range of educational fields, including art and culture, sports and physical activity, STEM, sustainability, socio-emotional competencies, civic/citizenship competencies, assistance in learning/tutoring, etc.).

The participants were heads of institutions or individuals responsible for educational programmes.

3 Data collection start/end date

October 9th 2023 – March 9th 2024

4 Samples by country

Country	Partner	Questionnaire language version	Sample size
Austria	AE	German	19
Croatia	ISRZ	Croatian	53
Finland	UOULU	Finnish	114
France	ALTEREURO	French	32
Greece	LATRA	Greek	183
Ireland	TCD	English	45
Netherlands	WAAG	Dutch	10
Slovenia	KERSNIKOVA	Slovenian	25
Spain	UB	Spanish	18
Spain	UB	Catalan	22
TOTAL			521

5 Dataset preparation

Datasets for each language form of “DHQ – Non-formal educational programmes” (10 versions) containing only complete cases were prepared.

Individual datasets were merged into an international dataset.

To ensure anonymisation, all variables related to participants' location and IP addresses were removed. Only anonymised data is made publicly available.

At the beginning of dataset, following four administrative variables were added:

- ID (educational institution identifier),
- Type of DHQ questionnaire,
- Country code
- Language of DHQ.

During data preparation process, the dataset was checked for completeness, aberrant codes and consistency in response patterns (limited to the segment of background variables).

Missing data responses were coded as -1 across all variables. Only in exceptional cases aberrant responses were recoded as missing data.

No weighting has been applied to the dataset.

6 Variable report

6.1 Administrative variables

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ID
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Non-formal educational institution ID
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	Numbers (1-n)
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Educational institution identifier

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	qtn_type
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Type of DHQ questionnaire
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 School 2 Educational institution providing non-formal programmes
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Identification of the DHQ version

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	country
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Country
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Austria 2 Croatia 3 Finland 4 France 5 Greece 6 Ireland 7 Netherlands 8 Slovenia 9 Spain
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Country of questionnaire administration
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	qnt_language
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Language of DHQ
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 German 2 Catalan 3 Croatian 4 Finnish 5 French 6 Greek 7 English 8 Dutch 9 Slovenian 10 Spanish
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Identification of language version of DHQ

6.2 Background variables

ITEM NUMBER	Q1
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	education_target_group
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Provide educational programmes for participants aged between 11 and 18
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	We provide educational programmes for participants aged between 11 and 18?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> yes <input type="radio"/> no
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 yes 2 no

ITEM NUMBER	Q2
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	public_private
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Public vs. private educational institution
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	We are?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<p><input type="radio"/> a public organisation - managed directly or indirectly by a public education authority, government agency, or governing board appointed by the government or elected by public franchise</p> <p><input type="radio"/> a private organisation - managed directly or indirectly by a non-government organisation, e.g. a church, trade union, business, or other private institution</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	<p>1 a public organisation</p> <p>2 a private organisation</p> <p>-1 N.A./missing</p>

ITEM NUMBER	Q3
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	profil_nonprofit
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	For-profit vs. non-profit educational institution
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	We are?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> a for-profit organisation <input type="radio"/> a non-profit organisation
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 a for-profit organisation 2 a non-profit organisation -1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q4
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_onsite_online
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Onsite vs. online educational programmes
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our educational programmes take place...
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> completely onsite <input type="radio"/> primarily onsite, but some programmes are online <input type="radio"/> primarily online, but some programmes are onsite <input type="radio"/> completely online
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 completely onsite 2 primarily onsite, but some programmes are online 3 primarily online, but some programmes are onsite 4 completely online -1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q5
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	location
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes location
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our educational programmes are primarily organised ...
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> in a rural area, village or small settlements with fewer than 3,000 people <input type="radio"/> in a small town (3,000 to 15,000 people) <input type="radio"/> in a town (15,000 to 100,000 people) <input type="radio"/> in a city (100,000 to 1,000,000 people) <input type="radio"/> in a large city (with over 1,000,000 people) <input type="radio"/> in a larger region <input type="radio"/> whole country/nationally <input type="radio"/> internationally
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 in a rural area, village, or settlement with fewer than 3,000 people 2 in a small town (3,000 to 15,000 people) 3 in a town (15,000 to 100,000 people) 4 in a city (100,000 to 1,000,000 people) 5 in a large city (with over 1,000,000 people) 6 in a larger region 7 whole country/nationally 8 internationally -1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q6
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_number
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Total number of participants aged 11 to 18 in the previous calendar year
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the total number of participants aged 11 to 18 in educational programmes you provided in the previous calendar year.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q7
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	financing_education
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Free of charge vs. paid
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our educational programmes are...?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> free of charge for participants <input type="radio"/> paid for by participants <input type="radio"/> some programs are free for participants and some are paid for by participants
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 free of charge for participants 2 paid for by participants 3 some programmes are free for participants and some are paid for by participants -1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q8
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_percent_diff_language
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Percentage of participants whose first language is different from the language of instruction
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the percentage of participants in your educational programmes whose first language is different from the language of instruction.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q9
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_percent_ed_needs
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Percentage of participants with additional educational needs
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the percentage of participants in your educational programmes with additional educational needs.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q10
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_percent_dis_socecon
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Percentage of participants from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the percentage of participants in your educational programmes from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q11
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_artsculture
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Arts and culture
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Arts and culture
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q12
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_sport
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Sport and physical activity
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Sport and physical activity
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q13
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_STEM
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: STEM
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for STEM
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q14
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_health
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Health
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Health
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q15
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_sustainability
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Sustainability
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Sustainability
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q16
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_language
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Language competencies
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Language competencies
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q17
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_socioemotional
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Socio-emotional competencies
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Socio-emotional competencies
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q18
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_ entrepreneurship
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Entrepreneurial competencies
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Entrepreneurial competencies
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q19
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_ civiccitizenship
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Civic/citizenship competencies
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Civic/citizenship competencies
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q20
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_cognitive
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Cognitive development
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Cognitive development
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q21
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	eduprogramme_assistance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Assistance in learning/ tutoring
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Assistance in learning/ tutoring
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q22
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	Eduprogramme_practical
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Practical skills
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Practical skills
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q23
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	Eduprogramme_digital
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Digital competencies
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Digital competencies
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q24
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	Eduprogramme_media
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes in: Media literacy
VARIABLE TYPE	Binary
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our organisation currently provides educational programmes for participants aged 11-18 in the following area(s)? <i>(Multiple responses are possible)</i>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	Checkbox Yes for Media literacy
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Yes

ITEM NUMBER	Q25
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	Eduprogramme_other
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Write in: Other
VARIABLE TYPE	String (open response)
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Other: <input type="text"/>
ANSWER CATEGORIES	-
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-

ITEM NUMBER	Q27
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development1_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Staff members are encouraged to propose ideas for new educational programmes. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.1. Staff members are encouraged to propose ideas for new educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q28
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development1_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Staff members are encouraged to propose ideas for new educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.1. Staff members are encouraged to propose ideas for new educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q30
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>A.2. Educational programmes are developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q31
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.2. Educational programmes are developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q32
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.3. Educational programmes are developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q33
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.3. Educational programmes are developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q34
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.3. Educational programmes are developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q35
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development4_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.4. Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q36
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development4_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of educational programmes. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.4. Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q37
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development4_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.4. Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>A horizontal scale from 0 to 100. The scale is marked at intervals of 10. Above the scale, there are three labels: "Not at all (0%)", "Somewhat (50%)", and "Very much (100%)". A grey circle is positioned at the 0 mark, and a grey line extends to the 100 mark.</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q38
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development5_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the process of development of educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.5. A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the process of development of educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q39
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development5_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the process of development of educational programmes. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.5. A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the process of development of educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q40
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development5_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the process of development of educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.5. A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the process of development of educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p> <p></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q4I
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development6_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Decisions about the educational programmes are collaborative. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.6. Decisions about the educational programmes are collaborative. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q42
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development6_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Decisions about the educational programmes are collaborative. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.6. Decisions about the educational programmes are collaborative. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q43
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development6_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Decisions about the educational programmes are collaborative. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.6. Decisions about the educational programmes are collaborative. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q44
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	accessl_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.1. Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q45
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access _currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the educational programmes. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.1. Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q46
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access1_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>B.1. Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the educational programmes. EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q46
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access2_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Ensuring access to educational programmes for participants from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.2. Ensuring access to educational programmes for participants from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q47
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Ensuring access to educational programmes for participants from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>B.2. Ensuring access to educational programmes for participants from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q48
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Ensuring access to educational programmes for participants from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>B.2. Ensuring access to educational programmes for participants from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q50
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Information about educational programmes and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.3. Information about educational programmes and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q51
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Information about educational programmes and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.3. Information about educational programmes and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q52
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery1_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants have the opportunity to influence the content of educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.1. Participants have the opportunity to influence the content of educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q53
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery1_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants have the opportunity to influence the content of educational programmes. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.1. Participants have the opportunity to influence the content of educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q54
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery1_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants have the opportunity to influence the content of educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.1. Participants have the opportunity to influence the content of educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q55
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery2_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods used in educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>C.2. Participants have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods used in educational programmes.</p> <p>IMPORTANCE</p> <p><i>How important do you consider this practice?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q58
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are based on teaching and learning methods that encourage active participation. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.3. Educational programmes are based on teaching and learning methods that encourage active participation. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q59
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are based on teaching and learning methods that encourage active participation. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.3. Educational programmes are based on teaching and learning methods that encourage active participation. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q60
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Educational programmes are based on teaching and learning methods that encourage active participation. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>C.3. Educational programmes are based on teaching and learning methods that encourage active participation.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q61
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery4_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.4. The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q62
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery4_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.4. The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q63
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery4_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.4. The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q64
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery5_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individualised support is provided for participants with additional educational needs. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.5. Individualised support is provided for participants with additional educational needs. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q65
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery5_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individualised support is provided for participants with additional educational needs. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.5. Individualised support is provided for participants with additional educational needs. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q66
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery5_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individualised support is provided for participants with additional educational needs. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.5. Individualised support is provided for participants with additional educational needs. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q68
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery6_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	In the educational programmes, participants are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within the group. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.6. In the educational programmes, participants are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within the group. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q69
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery6_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	In the educational programmes, participants are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within the group. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.6. In the educational programmes, participants are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within the group. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q70
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery7_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	All participants, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete the educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.7. All participants, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete the educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q71
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery7_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	All participants, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete the educational programmes. – CURRENT STATUS
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.7. All participants, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete the educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-top: 5px;"> <div style="flex: 1; border-bottom: 2px solid black; position: relative;"> <div style="position: absolute; left: 0; top: -10px; width: 100%; text-align: center;">0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</div> <div style="position: absolute; left: 0; top: 5px; width: 5%; background-color: grey; border-radius: 50%;"></div> </div> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q72
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery7_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	All participants, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete the educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.7. All participants, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete the educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q73
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery8_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants' rights and responsibilities within the educational programmes are clearly defined and communicated. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>C.8. Participants' rights and responsibilities within the educational programmes are clearly defined and communicated.</p> <p>IMPORTANCE</p> <p><i>How important do you consider this practice?</i></p>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">Not at all (0%)</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">Somewhat (50%)</div> <div style="margin-left: auto; text-align: right;">Very much (100%)</div> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-top: 5px;"> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">0</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">10</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">20</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">30</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">40</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">50</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">60</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">70</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">80</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">90</div> <div style="text-align: center;">100</div> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q74
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery8_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants' rights and responsibilities within the educational programmes are clearly defined and communicated. – CURRENT STATUS
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.8. Participants' rights and responsibilities within the educational programmes are clearly defined and communicated. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q75
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery8_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants' rights and responsibilities within the educational programmes are clearly defined and communicated. – EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.8. Participants' rights and responsibilities within the educational programmes are clearly defined and communicated. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q76
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery9_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either participants' or educators' rights. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.9. Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either participants' or educators' rights. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q77
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery9_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either participants’ or educators’ rights. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.9. Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either participants’ or educators’ rights. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q78
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery9_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either participants' or educators' rights. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.9. Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either participants' or educators' rights. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q79
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery10_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Conflicts that arise during the course of programme delivery are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.10. Conflicts that arise during the course of programme delivery are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q80
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery10_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Conflicts that arise during the course of programme delivery are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. – CURRENT STATUS
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.10. Conflicts that arise during the course of programme delivery are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q81
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery10_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Conflicts that arise during the course of programme delivery are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>C.10. Conflicts that arise during the course of programme delivery are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q83
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery11_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Programme delivery incorporates responsibility for the natural and social environment. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.II. Programme delivery incorporates responsibility for the natural and social environment. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>A horizontal scale bar ranging from 0 to 100. The scale is divided into 10% increments. Labels include 'Not at all (0%)', 'Somewhat (50%)', and 'Very much (100%)'. A grey circle is positioned at the 0 mark.</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q84
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery11_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Programme delivery incorporates responsibility for the natural and social environment. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.11. Programme delivery incorporates responsibility for the natural and social environment. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q85
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpactl_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.1. Participants' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q87
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpactl_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.1. Participants' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p style="text-align: center;">Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q89
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Outcomes of educational programmes are shared and discussed with the wider community. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.2. Outcomes of educational programmes are shared and discussed with the wider community. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q90
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Outcomes of educational programmes are shared and discussed with the wider community. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.2. Outcomes of educational programmes are shared and discussed with the wider community. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	Not at all (0%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q91
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants develop competencies for active citizenship through educational programmes. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.3. Participants develop competencies for active citizenship through educational programmes. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q92
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants develop competencies for active citizenship through educational programmes. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.3. Participants develop competencies for active citizenship through educational programmes. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q93
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participants develop competencies for active citizenship through educational programmes. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.3. Participants develop competencies for active citizenship through educational programmes. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q94
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact4_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Evaluation of educational programmes considers multiple indicators. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.4. Evaluation of educational programmes considers multiple indicators. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	Not at all (0%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q95
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact4_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Evaluation of educational programmes considers multiple indicators. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.4. Evaluation of educational programmes considers multiple indicators. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q97
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact5_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The impact of educational programmes on the wider community is evaluated. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.5. The impact of educational programmes on the wider community is evaluated. IMPORTANCE How important do you consider this practice?
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q98
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact5_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The impact of educational programmes on the wider community is evaluated. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.5. The impact of educational programmes on the wider community is evaluated. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q99
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact5_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The impact of educational programmes on the wider community is evaluated. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.5. The impact of educational programmes on the wider community is evaluated. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q100
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact6_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.6. Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q101
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact6_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.6. Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q102
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact6_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.6. Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

6.4 Main variables – democratic values

ITEM NUMBER	Q103
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	participation_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participation - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Participation refers to the active involvement of participants, staff, and other stakeholders in the programme development, learning process, and overall functioning of the institution. It goes beyond mere attendance and encompasses engagement, interaction, collaboration, and contribution within the educational community.</p> <p>IMPORTANCE</p> <p><i>How important do you consider this value?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 Somewhat (50%) 60 70 80 90 100 Very much (100%)</p> <p></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q104
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	participation_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participation – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Participation refers to the active involvement of participants, staff, and other stakeholders in the programme development, learning process, and overall functioning of the institution. It goes beyond mere attendance and encompasses engagement, interaction, collaboration, and contribution within the educational community.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this value currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q105
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	participation_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participation - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Participation refers to the active involvement of participants, staff, and other stakeholders in the programme development, learning process, and overall functioning of the institution. It goes beyond mere attendance and encompasses engagement, interaction, collaboration, and contribution within the educational community.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q107
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	acctrans_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Accountability and transparency – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Accountability and transparency ensures that the institution is responsible for its actions, decisions, and outcomes while maintaining an open and honest relationship with its internal and external stakeholders. It fosters openness and accessibility of information related to the functioning, decision-making processes, and performance of an educational institution.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this value currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q109
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	EDI_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Equality, diversity, and inclusion – IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) presumes institutional dedication towards equal representation and opportunities, as well as respect and justice for participants from various backgrounds, such as ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, and abilities. Institutions that value EDI foster a sense of belonging, seek diverse perspectives, and encourage engagement to maximise the potential of every individual.</p> <p>IMPORTANCE</p> <p><i>How important do you consider this value?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q111
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	EDI_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Equality, diversity, and inclusion - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) presumes institutional dedication towards equal representation and opportunities, as well as respect and justice for participants from various backgrounds, such as ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, and abilities. Institutions that value EDI foster a sense of belonging, seek diverse perspectives, and encourage engagement to maximise the potential of every individual.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q112
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ecosocresp_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Eco-social responsibility - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Eco-social responsibility refers to the ethical obligation and accountability the institution has towards the environment and society, recognising their interconnectedness and advocating for sustainable practices that minimise harm to both. Eco-social responsibility encourages actions that prioritise environmental conservation, social justice, and the wellbeing of the wider community, aiming for a more equitable and sustainable future. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this value?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q113
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ecosocresp_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Eco-social responsibility – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Eco-social responsibility refers to the ethical obligation and accountability the institution has towards the environment and society, recognising their interconnectedness and advocating for sustainable practices that minimise harm to both. Eco-social responsibility encourages actions that prioritise environmental conservation, social justice, and the wellbeing of the wider community, aiming for a more equitable and sustainable future.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this value currently present in educational programmes of your organisation?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q114
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ecosocresp_expectation - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Eco-social responsibility
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Eco-social responsibility refers to the ethical obligation and accountability the institution has towards the environment and society, recognising their interconnectedness and advocating for sustainable practices that minimise harm to both. Eco-social responsibility encourages actions that prioritise environmental conservation, social justice, and the wellbeing of the wider community, aiming for a more equitable and sustainable future. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in educational programmes of your organisation in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 Very much (100%)</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

